

The objective of RESiLEX is to improve the resilience and sustainability of the entire Silicon value chain and reduce EU dependence on critical raw materials for solar panel and battery production. Silicon is considered a critical raw material for the EU due to its high supply risk and economic importance, mainly because of heavy reliance on imports

Circular Metal Recovery from Mining Waste

A view of the mine called *Filón Norte*, located in Spain and no more in operation. Before mining can restart, the acid wastewaters seen in the picture must be removed and treated

Mining waste, the issue to solve

The handling of mining waste is not an easy task, but it could turn into an opportunity to recover critical raw materials. In particular, pollution from Acid Mine Drainage (AMD) is often stored in open basins, requiring expensive remediation. Mining companies are legally obligated to treat these waters if they intend to restart or maintain extraction activities. In the RESiLEX project, the collaboration between Tharsis Mining (a Spanish mining company) and Cetaqua (a Veolia group research center), stems from the need to treat AMD in Spain.

Instead of using conventional lime treatments—which are costly and generate unusable waste—the RESiLEX project developed a circular economy approach. The goal is twofold: to reduce environmental impact and to recover Critical Raw and Strategic Materials (CRSMs) such as cobalt, nickel and copper as well as other valuable metals such as zinc, which are essential for the European production of batteries and solar panels.

Implementation of the treatment system

An innovative treatment pathway consisting of eight sequential units was created, divided between the valorization of wastewater and solid waste.

Wastewater Pathway (developed by Cetaqua):

- **Iron and Aluminum Removal:** An initial physico-chemical unit precipitates these metals by adding caustic soda.
- **Anaerobic Bioreactor (AnMBR):** Uses bacteria and organic waste (glycerin) to generate the sulfides necessary for metal precipitation.
- **Sulfide Precipitation:** Copper and zinc are recovered in the form of metal sulfides.
- **Ion Exchange (IEX):** Specific resins selectively retain cobalt and nickel.
- **Acid Recovery and Crystallization:** Through nanofiltration and evaporation, metals are concentrated into cobalt and nickel sulfate crystals, while sulfuric acid is recovered for reuse within the system.

Solid Waste Pathway (developed by Tharsis Mining):

- **Thermal Oxidation (Roasting):** Solid waste with high sulfur content is treated in a rotary kiln to produce sulfur dioxide (SO₂).
- **Sulfuric Acid Production:** The gas is converted into sulfuric acid (H₂SO₄), which directly feeds the ion exchange unit for metal recovery.

Scheme depicting the valorisation routes followed by Tharsis mining (Mine waste) and Cetaqua (Acid wastewater)

Key Results, Business Model, and Strategic Implications

The system has demonstrated that it is technically and economically feasible to transform waste into a strategic resource.

- **Technical Results**: The treatment reduces acid water discharge by 90% compared to current scenarios. Crystals composed of 18% Co (cobalt) and 6% Nickel were obtained, ready to be reused as industrial intermediates.
- **Business Model**: The net treatment cost is estimated at €1.24 per cubic meter of water, a significantly lower value compared to the €4.12 of conventional lime treatment. Revenue is generated from the sale of recovered metals (especially cobalt sulfate hepta- or hexahydrated, which has a high market value) and savings achieved by internally reusing the sulfuric acid produced from solid waste. These metals can be sold as intermediate products for metallurgical sectors or for the production of pigments and coatings.
- **Strategic Implications**: This work directly supports the objectives of the European Union's Critical Raw Materials Act, reducing dependence on foreign imports of materials for the energy transition. Furthermore, it offers a model for the sustainable reactivation of abandoned mines in Europe, transforming environmental liabilities into circular and resilient mining hubs.

View of the second segment of *Filòn Norte*

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RESiLEX Project

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Co-funded by
the European Union

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Project funded by

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Swiss Confederation

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Education and Research EAER
State Secretariat for Education,
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